

The AI Project Lifecycle: Implementation Strategies and Tools

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Abstract

A successful artificial intelligence (AI) project passes through multiple stages, many of which may be advanced by the use of beyond-desktop research computing and data (RCD) resources. In this paper, we outline the key stages of the AI project lifecycle and describe: the typical tasks a researcher must undertake at each stage; the types of user tools that may be employed; when RCD resources are most likely to enable or advance the work; and when engagement with RCD professionals is most beneficial. This paper is intended to help early- and mid-career RCD professionals understand the AI project lifecycle and assess infrastructure needs across its stages so they can more effectively support research teams. The goal is to present a framework that encourages RCD professionals to move beyond a purely supportive role and toward a more collaborative partnership with researchers and practitioners.

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1 Introduction

In an Artificial Intelligence (AI) landscape defined by rapid change and growing institutional demand, Research Computing and Data (RCD) professionals play a critical role in bridging exploratory research and sustainable technology. They do this by collaborating with researchers, educators, students, staff, and external partners to “co-create” solutions that address complex computing and data needs[1, 2]. Building on our prior work on an AI project lifecycle framework[1], this paper offers, from an RCD perspective, a practitioner-oriented guide to the tools and processes that can be used at each stage of the AI project lifecycle (Figure 1). Our goal is to help research teams move from exploratory ideas to reliable, reproducible, scalable, and sustainable AI capabilities, while balancing performance, cost, security, privacy, and responsible use of shared institutional and, when applicable, national RCD resources. The need for structured AI integration within RCD is reflected across national discussions by organizations and initiatives like CASC, the NSF AI Institutes and NAIRR Pilot, and ACCESS whom collectively emphasize strategic investment in cyberinfrastructure, workforce development, security, and policy to enable effective, sustainable, and responsible AI adoption and support at scale[3, 4, 5, 6, 7]. This work, supported in part by NSF OAC Award #2436057, leverages the Campus Research Computing Consortium (CaRCC)’s[8] national RCD professional network—particularly the AI Facilitation Materials Working Group[9] and, more broadly, the AI Facilitation Interest Group[10]—to translate an AI project lifecycle model into actionable guidance that empowers RCD professionals and researchers across the community. The remainder of this paper introduces the full lifecycle of an AI-based workflow, details its constituent stages, and presents concrete tools and implementation strategies that RCD professionals can adopt to facilitate successful AI projects at their institutions.

Figure 1: Conceptual illustration of the AI project lifecycle stages from inception to completion

2 AI Project Lifecycle and Methodology

The project lifecycle of an AI-based workflow consists of multiple stages as illustrated in Figure 1. Each of these stages are necessary for processing and analyzing the input data accurately and address the problem at hand efficiently. Together they form the pipeline of an AI project lifecycle that, if implemented correctly, completes the project successfully.

Given that AI’s impact spans a wide range of research areas, an AI project lifecycle that generalizes across diverse real-world use cases is essential. Regardless of the specific application, AI-based projects typically follow a common, multi-stage workflow in which the output of each stage becomes the input to the next. To achieve this in a practical way, we organized our RCD-facing guidance into a stage-based AI project lifecycle that maps each stage to concrete tools, processes, and decision points that help RCD professionals and research teams progress from exploration to reproducible, scalable, sustainable and responsibly managed outcomes. Our approach used a qualitative document-analysis of peer-reviewed literature, authoritative white papers, frameworks, and community guidance; furthermore, we applied triangulation to compare multiple credible sources and conducted member checking with RCD professionals in our working group to refine clarity and applicability[11]. We divide each stage into multiple sub-sections. Each sub-section delineates the typical tasks performed by a researcher or a developer during that stage and the tools needed to perform those tasks. We start with the foundation stage of any AI project lifecycle, which is *Problem Definition & Planning*.

2.1 Problem Definition & Planning

Problem definition and planning is the critical first stage in the AI project lifecycle that frames a research problem (or operational improvement) that they aim to solve into an AI-ready effort that is feasible, compliant, and measurable[12]. Detailed project-management mechanics is outside of the scope for this paper, instead, our emphasis is on disciplined framing and early risk reduction from an RCD professional lens. Problem definition scopes the work into a clear, testable problem (often iteratively) with measurable success criteria (define what “good” is). Planning ensures the proposed approach aligns with institutional RCD capabilities and constraints, including data readiness (source, volume, compliance with regulatory frameworks such as NIST 800-171), governance obligations, and cyberinfrastructure requirements (compute, storage, networking, software environments, and on-prem vs. cloud feasibility)[13, 14]. This stage of the project should produce products like a one-page problem statement and a project plan that make objectives, assumptions, constraints, and evaluation expectations visible and traceable.

Project Plan: A one-page problem statement should clearly define the research problem from an RCD perspective, including objectives, scope, success criteria, and resource budget. This is translated into a high-level project plan that explicitly outlines key milestones, estimated timelines, dependencies, risks, and mitigation strategies. Through co-design, the plan is further refined by including and interviewing key stakeholders (e.g., stakeholder map). During planning, the project is aligned with institutional and sponsor policies, including required reviews (e.g., cybersecurity assessment, IRB, legal/privacy)[12]. During planning, the project team identifies data sources, expected volumes, determines data sensitivity and regulatory classification (e.g., PII, PHI, CUI), along with required Data Use Agreements (DUA). Also, we recommend identifying clear decision points (go/no-go checkpoints) for data access/readiness, approvals and governance alignment, resource readiness (including security posture), evaluation, and alignment with RCD capabilities at each stage, including scoping out compute, storage, network and software needs along with on-prem vs. cloud feasibility[13, 14].

To facilitate the activities of this stage, use standard project-management templates where available; otherwise, document and track the plan using established intake and planning tools such as commercial and open-source tools. Also, use the institution’s standard data management planning process (e.g., DMPTool) to capture data requirements, which we further expand and discuss in the next stage, *Data Preparation*[15].

2.2 Data Preparation

Data preparation for an AI-based workflow involves acquiring, cleaning, transforming, exploring, and curating raw data to make it suitable for further processing and analysis. This includes gathering an understanding of how it was created and collected, identifying its type (numerical, categorical, time series, mixed), why it is needed, what it signifies, its statistical summary, what its edge cases are, and what type of problem needs to be addressed with it[16]. Typical tasks that a researcher might need to perform during this stage, and the tools needed to perform them, are:

Data Cleaning involves removing duplicates, handling outliers, and dealing with missing values, formatting issues, and/or errors. The **Quality Assurance** task involves ensuring the quality of the data, removing bias, and checking for data completeness, consistency, and outliers using tools, such as custom scripts (Python/R) based on data version control (DVC) methods and Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) principles[12]. **Privacy** considerations include removing, masking, or swapping identifiers, aggregating sensitive fields, and documenting methods to support transparency and privacy compliance[17]. When formal privacy guarantees are required, differential privacy libraries such as OpenDP, SmartNoise, PyDP, and diffprivlib provide implementable frameworks for protecting individual records while enabling statistical analysis. The **Transformation** process involves preparing raw data for data analysis and engineering. This includes normalizing and scaling, performing data augmentation (for modalities such as audio, image, and video), indexing data, applying text tokenization, and optimizing storage and query performance. The **Exploratory Data Analysis** process is about visualizing distributions, spotting anomalies, patterns, and correlations. **Feature Engineering** involves creating, selecting, transforming, encoding, and reducing the dimensionality of features, as well as addressing multicollinearity.

Reproducibility & Versioning involves tracking data transformations and versions to ensure transparency and enable researchers to replicate the past efforts (e.g., simulations) using tools like git and DVC[18]. The common tools used for this stage include, but are not limited to, OpenRefine, Python (scikit-learn, Pandas, spaCy, Faker, FeatureTools, Matplotlib, Seaborn, Plotly, Bokeh), R (dplyr, stringr, tidytext, tidyverse, tidymodels, data.table, sdcMicro, anonymizer, ggplot2), integrated development environments (IDEs), ARX, Excel, custom scripts, Hadoop/Spark. The data prepared during this stage is used downstream for the *Model Selection and/or Development* stage as that informs the model that should be selected based on the problem at hand and the data associated with it.

2.3 Model Selection and/or Development

Model selection and/or development is the lifecycle phase where teams decide whether to adopt, adapt, or build a model to meet the project’s research goals. It translates planning and data preparation work into concrete choices about model family, licensing, compliance, compute feasibility, and evaluation standards—often involving, but not limited to, foundation models (LLMs/vision/multimodal). For AI facilitation, the emphasis is on making these choices explicit, documented, and testable so that the project can proceed to downstream stages with clear decision points. Common tasks and tools used during this stage are described below.

Assess candidate models and baselines involves identifying plausible model families for the research question and constraints, then comparing them against strong baselines before committing to adaptation or training. It includes checking modality fit (text, vision, multimodal), interpretability requirements, robustness expectations, and feasibility given data availability and compute access. One needs to evaluate foundation model options thoroughly based on specific research needs and available resources. One can start with open foundation models before attempting to train from scratch. They can check a model registry (e.g., site-, cloud-, or personally hosted) and various “Model Zoos”, like Hugging Face, Nvidia NGC. For smaller experiments with limited budgets, one can utilize

Colab Pro or Kaggle before scaling to institutional resources. This staged approach preserves costly HPC allocations for production-scale training and lowers the barrier to entry for researchers new to AI workflows. Common tools include scikit-learn and XGBoost for classical baselines, PyTorch and TensorFlow/Keras for neural baselines, and standardized metric utilities such as Hugging Face evaluation tooling to keep comparisons consistent across runs.

Verify licensing, usage rights, and governance task focuses on confirming that the selected model, weights, datasets, and any external services can be used for the project’s intended purpose (e.g., research vs. commercial, redistribution restrictions, attribution requirements) and that the workflow aligns with institutional policy—especially when sensitive data are involved. In practice, teams rely on model cards and licensing metadata from model hubs, vendor documentation for commercial models and APIs, and internal governance checklists or review processes to document approvals and constraints[19].

Select an adaptation strategy choice involves choosing parameter-efficient tuning, full fine-tuning, or training from scratch based on the project’s success criteria, available labeled data, and compute budget. It often includes estimating runtime and cost, deciding where training should occur (HPC vs cloud), and selecting an approach that meets privacy and compliance requirements. When fine-tuning large models, leverage parameter-efficient techniques like PEFT/LoRA with sharding to reduce memory requirements[20]. Other common tools include Hugging Face Transformers for development and distributed training utilities in PyTorch/TensorFlow to manage memory, throughput, and multi-GPU scaling. For multimodal applications, consider specialized models like DALL-E, Stable Diffusion, or Flamingo rather than building custom solutions.

Prepare training, validation, and test pipelines process involves assembling f–datasets, defining preprocessing steps, establishing reproducible splits, and assessing computational resources needs. When computational resources are limited, consider leveraging pre-trained weights rather than training from scratch, as this can reduce data requirements from petabytes (PB) to gigabytes (GB) or terabytes (TB). Utilize Hugging Face Datasets for standardized dataset handling, and workflow systems, such as Snakemake or Nextflow, for pipelines that need formal orchestration. The **Run experiments and track model lineage** ensures that every run can be reproduced and compared by capturing code versions, dataset versions, configuration parameters, environment details, and artifacts such as checkpoints and logs. It supports systematic iteration, credible reporting, and smoother hand-offs to benchmarking or deployment. Common tools include Git for code versioning, DVC for data and artifact versioning, and experiment tracking platforms such as MLflow, ClearML, or Weights & Biases, often paired with shared filesystems or object storage for large checkpoint files[17].

Evaluate model quality, robustness, and bias measures performance against success criteria and benchmarks, identifies failure modes, and, where relevant, assesses fairness and subgroup performance differences. It often includes error analysis, calibration checks, and interpretability work to understand where and why the model fails. Common tools include scikit-learn metrics for performance reporting, TensorBoard for training diagnostics, Fairlearn for fairness evaluation, and explanation toolkits such as SHAP and LIME to support interpretability and stakeholder review[21]. The model selected or developed during this stage forms the input for the next stage where it is trained and tuned to obtain a generalized model.

2.4 Model Training & Tuning

The model training and tuning stage is about optimizing model parameters and hyperparameters through iterative learning to enable a model that can generalize from data. Typical tasks performed by researchers during this stage are described below.

The process begins with **configuring the training**, where researchers set essential hyperparameters such as learning rate, batch size, and epochs to control the optimization process, often using four-

dational libraries (e.g., Python, Tensorflow, PyTorch, Keras, scikit-learn)[22]. As the model trains, continuous **monitoring** is essential to track loss curves and other metrics on both training and validation sets, which helps in detecting issues like slow convergence or overfitting (e.g., Weights & Biases, MLflow, Comet.ml, SageMaker/Vertex AI dashboards). To **improve model stability and generalization**, various techniques such as regularization, dropout, early stopping, and mixed-precision are applied to prevent overfitting, typically within an integrated development environment (e.g., Jupyter, Visual Studio Code, PyCharm) and with the help of specialized callbacks (e.g., Keras/TensorFlow). **Training** involves launching jobs on single or multiple GPUs or nodes, where managing resources and checkpoints is critical (e.g., Slurm, Kubernetes, Singularity/Apptainer, Conda/Mamba). Finally, to refine the model, researchers engage in **hyperparameter search and experimentation**, defining and exploring hyperparameter space through systematic methods like grid search, random search, or Bayesian optimization. This involves running multiple trials and **applying these search strategies** to find the best model configurations, leveraging specialized tools and platforms including Ray Tune, Optuna, Hyperopt, Google Cloud AutoML, Azure AutoML, and model repositories such as Hugging Face Hub. The trained and tuned model is now ready to be benchmarked, optimized, and quality controlled before it is ready for deployment. The next section describes the benchmarking, optimization, and quality control stage in detail.

2.5 Model Benchmarking, Optimization, and Quality Control

Model benchmarking evaluates AI models on well-defined tasks using specified datasets, metrics, protocols, and hardware configurations. It measures model quality (e.g., accuracy), efficiency (latency, throughput, and cost), scalability, and robustness, including reliability and bias. Benchmarking provides objective evidence for model comparison and selection and establishes baseline performance expectations. Typical user tasks include **defining evaluation objectives and success metrics** such as accuracy, F1 score, BLEU, mAP, latency, cost per token, and energy usage; **selecting baseline or competing models** for comparison; and **preparing public or internal benchmark datasets** (e.g., GLUE, SQuAD, ImageNet[23, 24, 25]). For standardized performance evaluation across systems, MLCommons[26], an open consortium, publishes open, state-of-art industry-standard AI/ML benchmarks and results from participating institutions. Reproducible benchmarking environments are created using containerized or virtual environments. **Benchmark execution** involves controlling batch sizes, documenting hardware and software configurations, and managing experiments, followed by **result analysis** to compare against baselines or state-of-the-art performance and identify performance bottlenecks. MLflow[27], among others, is an excellent tool to manage the benchmarking experiments.

Model optimization is an iterative process aimed at improving computational efficiency and scalability while balancing accuracy and cost. Optimization enhances deployment feasibility, user experience, and energy efficiency. Key tasks include **performance profiling** to identify latency, throughput, memory, and compute bottlenecks; applying **model-level optimization** such as hyperparameter tuning, pruning, and knowledge distillation[28]; and **improving computational efficiency** through quantization and parallel or distributed execution across multiple devices or nodes. These techniques enable models to scale efficiently while maintaining acceptable accuracy for production workloads. Common tools are PyTorch Profiler and TensorBoard for profiling; Pytorch Pruning and DistilBERT for model optimization, and NVIDIA TensorRT, GPTQ[29], and ONNX Runtime for quantization and parallelization.

Quality Control (QC) focuses on testing, auditing, and continuously monitoring models against acceptance criteria for performance, reliability, fairness, and regulatory compliance during development and after deployment. Typical tasks include **ensuring data integrity** throughout the data lifecycle using tools such as Great Expectations and Pandera; **validating models** by tracking key performance

metrics and detecting overfitting or underfitting, and performing detailed error analysis with tools such as TorchMetrics and Weights & Biases. Beyond standard performance evaluation, **robustness and safety assessments** examine fairness, explainability, and resilience to abnormal or adversarial conditions. IBM AI Fairness 360, SHAP, and LIME[30, 31] are great tools for evaluating a model’s robustness. **Stress testing** under extreme workloads further reduces operational risk and supports long-term system reliability. After the model has successfully passed benchmarking, optimization, and quality control, the model is considered **deployment-ready**, with known behavior, acceptable risk, and predictable behavior in production, which is discussed in the next section.

2.6 Model Deployment

After model benchmarking, optimization, and quality control confirm acceptable performance, reliability, and risk, the model can be packaged and deployed into research or production environments. **Model deployment** packages a trained model with its dependencies and integrates it into the target environment so it can perform inference on new data. It includes managing infrastructure and computational resources for **batch**, **interactive**, or **real-time** execution modes, along with monitoring, versioning, and scaling to ensure reliability and compliance within operational workflows.

Batch deployment commonly supports **model Inference for simulations and research analysis**, where trained models are applied to large datasets or simulated outputs using scheduled automated workflows. These workloads emphasize throughput, reproducibility, and cost efficiency and are often executed at scale on shared HPC resources. Batch deployment also typically includes **model packaging and environment setup**, where trained models are bundled with dependencies, configurations, and runtime environments to enable consistent execution across HPC systems. This step is critical for reproducibility and portability. Batch execution further supports **data-processing pipelines**, in which large research datasets are transformed, aggregated, or preprocessed prior to or alongside inference. Commonly supported tools include TensorFlow and PyTorch for inference, Slurm for job scheduling, Apache Spark MLlib for data-processing pipelines, and container or environment technologies such as Apptainer or Singularity, Docker, Conda environments, MLflow Models, and ONNX.

Interactive deployment enables on-demand model use by researchers and analysts, supporting rapid experimentation, validation, and exploration of model behavior. Interactive workflows commonly include **web-based model testing**, where users evaluate model outputs through notebooks or lightweight applications, and **Interactive visualization**, which supports inspection of predictions, intermediate outputs, or training behavioral in human-in-the-loop workflows. These activities prioritize usability and responsiveness and often rely on models and packaged environments produced during batch deployment. Interactive use frequently informs further refinement, benchmarking, or transition to operational serving. Commonly supporting platforms include Jupyter Notebook, JupyterLab, and JupyterHub, along with visualization and experiment-tracking tools such as TensorBoard, Weights & Biases (W&B), and Streamlit or Dash.

Real-time deployment supports inference for applications requiring immediate responses and integration with operational systems. Primary real-time activities include **API-based predictions**, where models are exposed programmatically to downstream systems, as well as **robotics**, **autonomous systems**, and **edge deployment**, which rely on continuous or event-driven inference for sensing, control, and decision-making. These workloads emphasize responsiveness, concurrency, and reliability under load and typically build on models that have already been trained, packaged, and interactively validated. Real-time systems may operate at scale or under strict latency constraints, requiring optimized inference pipelines. Commonly supported tools include FastAPI, BentoML, and Flask for serving interfaces, along with TensorFlow Serving, TorchServe, NVIDIA Triton, KServe, and ONNX Runtime.

Conversational AI tools support domain-specific chatbots and assistants that provide near-instant responses to user queries. These systems often integrate LLMs with optimized inference backends for real-time interaction. Typical tools include Hugging Face Inference API, NVIDIA Triton, Ollama, vLLM, and LiteLLM. However, overall security still depends on trusted model sources and proper system isolation.

Across all deployment modes, **model management and monitoring** are cross-cutting concerns that ensure deployed models remain reliable, reproducible, and fit for purpose over time. These activities include versioning, performance tracking, drift detection, and lifecycle management that inform retraining, revalidation, and redeployment as usage patterns or data distributions change. Common platforms supporting these capabilities include MLflow, ClearML, Weights & Biases, and Neptune.ai. Once deployed, the model produces predictions and outputs which must then be interpreted, evaluated, and communicated in the results interpretation and reporting stage.

2.7 Results Interpretation and Reporting

Results Interpretation and Reporting addresses how evaluation outputs from Model Benchmarking, QC, and Optimization are contextualized and conveyed in the post-deployment phase. Interpretation focuses on translating performance evidence into defensible conclusions about model behavior and intended use. These conclusions are shaped by earlier Problem Definition & Planning and Data Preparation decisions. Reporting disseminates results through appropriate summaries, visualizations, and supporting documentation for diverse audiences. Assumptions, uncertainties, and potential sources of bias are also articulated to provide context for responsible model use. An important outcome of this stage is the production of research artifacts. Common tasks and tools utilized during this phase include:

Evaluate Model Outputs involves assessing results in relation to the original research question and situating findings within the context of prior literature or established benchmarks. This work includes identifying patterns, anomalies, and failure modes in model behavior. Potential fairness or bias issues are also analyzed[32]. Common tools used for this work include scikit-learn metrics, yardstick, TensorFlow Model Analysis, SHAP, LIME, DALEX, and Fairlearn.

Visualize Results focuses on creating plots, diagrams, and interactive dashboards that support exploration and communication of model performance and behavior. This work is typically supported by tools such as Matplotlib, Seaborn, ggplot2, mlr3viz, Plotly, Shiny, and Streamlit, with SHAP and LIME commonly used to visualize model explanations.

Document Code, Parameters, and Dependencies ensures traceability of model results by capturing software environments, package versions, and hardware dependencies in standardized, machine-readable forms. Version control is commonly supported by tools such as Git while model documentation may be created using resources such as the Model Card Toolkit or Hugging Face Model Cards[19]. Execution environments are often captured using tools such as conda, pip freeze, or R renv, with containers such as Docker or Apptainer used to support portability across systems.

Archive / Publish Datasets treats the dataset as a distinct research output and emphasizes transparent reporting of its contents and provenance to support reproducibility and comply with research funding mandates[33]. Documentation typically includes licensing and metadata, while storage environments are selected to align with compute workflows, file formats, and access controls. Open repositories are used when data can be publicly shared and reuse is encouraged through the use of Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs). Datasets containing sensitive information are instead stored in restricted-access repositories or secure institutional research environments, including trusted research environments (TREs).

Prepare and Disseminate Research Outputs focuses on integrating results from model analyses and adapting them for different audiences. To support this work, researchers rely on authoring tools

with integrated version control and collaborative editing features, such as Overleaf, Google Workspace, and Microsoft Office. Quarto and Markdown workflows are used to support multi-format outputs. Final outputs are disseminated through appropriate scholarly channels, including journals, conference proceedings, preprint servers, and code repositories. DOIs are typically used to support discoverability and reuse. Depending on audience and impact goals, results may also be shared through grey literature and other public-facing channels, including white papers, press releases, or social media.

As research outputs are prepared for dissemination beyond the immediate research team, ethical commitments established during the project planning phase are enacted in practice. Decisions about how results are framed and which artifacts are disseminated shape the downstream impacts of AI research. In response, RCD professionals work with researchers to ensure that reporting and dissemination practices align with applicable governance requirements. This responsibility is especially pronounced for research involving Indigenous data. Responsible AI practice requires interpretation and reporting decisions to reflect Indigenous community authority over access, reuse, and the creation of derived model artifacts[34].

Every stage of an AI project lifecycle has areas where engaging with RCD professionals can prove to be extremely beneficial, especially when executed at the right time. Additionally, there are a few tips and tricks that might come in handy for troubleshooting issues while executing certain stages and how RCD teams can help. We discuss this in the following sections.

3 RCD Involvement

AI projects benefit from Research Computing and Data (RCD) support at every stage of the lifecycle, and that support is most effective when RCD teams are engaged early—during the problem definition and project planning stage. Early collaboration helps surface technical, regulatory, and cost constraints, align the project with available infrastructure, and avoid expensive rework later. Here, we delineate the situations on when to involve RCD and why.

Data volume, complexity, memory, and performance limits: When datasets exceed local storage/RAM, hit CPU or disk I/O bottlenecks, require high-bandwidth parallel filesystems, or training/ingestion jobs run for days and local hardware lacks the reliability or fault tolerance needed. RCD teams can help by moving workloads to HPC/cloud, setting up distributed processing (multi-GPU/multi-node), and tuning resource usage. They can also use burst buffers, NVMe caches, and data staging/compression to take the load off of the cluster’s storage filesystem.

Model scale, tuning, and benchmarking: For fine-tuning large models (e.g., GPT or Llama 2), implementing PEFT/LoRA, or when running extensive hyperparameter and AutoML jobs. RCD teams can help by guiding hardware selection (GPU type, memory, NVLink, CPU–GPU bandwidth), optimizing data pipelines, and choosing appropriate frameworks. They can help design rigorous benchmarks (data selection, fairness/bias metrics), containerize environments, configure job scripts, and set up profiling and monitoring tools (e.g., MLflow, TensorBoard, Nsight, PyTorch Profiler).

Compliance, privacy, and governance: Projects with PII, CUI, HIPAA/GDPR, FERPA obligations, Indigenous data sovereignty, or IRB constraints require early risk assessment and help navigating compliance and governance for sensitive and restricted data. RCD teams can provide secure storage, encryption, access control, and auditability, and can also offer guidance on differential privacy (libraries like opendp, SmartNoise, PyDP, diffprivlib), and help interpret policy and regulatory requirements.

Infrastructure architecture and cost management: When bridging on-prem clusters with academic cloud grants, or when cloud costs become prohibitive relative to data volume/job frequency. RCD teams can help by designing hybrid architectures (on-prem + cloud), estimating compute/storage costs, and right-sizing solutions between laptops/Colab and full clusters. They can also address the

lack of shared infrastructure by deploying shared filesystems and data platforms (e.g., Globus) to make data AI-ready.

Deployment, serving, and real-time workloads: For containerization, batch workflows, scalable serving, and real-time low-latency applications (e.g., drones, robotics, conversational AI). RCD teams can support schedulers for batch jobs, Kubernetes and Apptainer/Singularity for containerized serving, and specialized storage systems for mixed AI workloads (VAST, NetApp). They can also work with network teams to ensure high-bandwidth networking and interconnects and maintain inference frameworks (TensorFlow Serving, TorchServe, ONNX Runtime), and can lower barriers and provide user-friendly interfaces such as JupyterHub, Hugging Face APIs, Ollama, Streamlit/Dash, while using tools like MLflow/ClearML for lifecycle tracking and drift monitoring.

Interpretation, reporting, and ethics: When model outputs are hard to interpret, explain to non-technical audiences, or evaluate for fairness/bias. RCD teams can help by selecting appropriate metrics and visualizations, applying fairness tools (Fairlearn, AIF360), and using visual diagnostic packages (e.g., DALEX, mlr3viz) to catch issues earlier. They can also support thorough documentation of code, parameters, and hardware, and help capture computational environments for reproducibility (containers, dependency management).

Reproducibility, automation, and dissemination: Many teams rely on ad-hoc, manual pipelines and static documents (Word/PowerPoint), which undermines reproducibility and slows collaboration. Here, RCD teams can promote workflow automation (Snakemake, Nextflow, Airflow) and executable documents (Quarto, R Markdown, Jupyter Notebooks) for integrated analysis, figure generation, and reporting. They can also advise on handling proprietary data formats, encourage open/standard formats, and point to resources (e.g., format catalogs) and conversion tools, and can help select appropriate repositories (open or restricted) that match technical and regulatory needs and ensure that data, models, and logs are citable and reusable. Additionally they can provide templates, discipline-specific examples, and training (executive summaries, plain-language abstracts, equity-focused reporting) for broader communication and fairness reporting.

Cross-cutting principle: RCD teams cannot instantly fix deep infrastructure, compliance, or workflow issues; they need time to adapt software stacks, deploy shared systems, and coordinate with other institutional units, if needed. Making them aware of constraints as early as possible—and revisiting them iteratively as the AI project evolves—enables more robust, compliant, scalable, and reproducible AI workflows from data preparation through deployment and results communication.

Across all stages, sustainability is highlighted as a cross-cutting concern: AI’s high energy use and thermal load demand strategic investments in efficient cyberinfrastructure, cooling, energy audits, and tools that expose energy usage (e.g., Slurm energy accounting) to developers. This need is echoed through national conversations as discussed in recent CASC position papers[4, 35]. RCD professionals are called to promote energy-aware tooling, development environments, and behaviors to help researchers align their projects with the institution’s environmental and sustainability goals[6].

4 Conclusion and Future Work

Building on the prior paper[1] that defined the AI project lifecycle and its respective stages through an RCD lens, the CaRCC AI Facilitation Working Group provides this extended paper with detailed facilitation guidance for the AI lifecycle. This extended paper serves as a “practitioner’s manual” for RCD professionals and their campus partners.

A recurring implicit insight in this paper is that “late-stage pain” is often “early-stage debt.” Issues of fairness, anomalous behavior, interpretability, and reporting frequently surface late in the project lifecycle, but addressing these issues typically requires revisiting earlier decisions in scoping and planning, data preparation, or even model design. If left unaddressed, then this pattern drives

rework, researcher frustration, cost overruns, and delayed timelines. This is why this work is critical—it provides the guiding framework for facilitating AI projects that RCD professionals and researchers can use to identify risk earlier, align decisions across stages, and avoid these pitfalls.

In parallel, we have developed a complementary, web-based AI learning resources guide to be published on the CaRCC website that organizes more expansive stage-based materials and learning resources that span foundational concepts, tools, and ethical considerations, within a self-directed learning framework. Beyond providing learning materials for individual users, this web documentation provides a high-quality knowledge base for Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) enabled AI chatbot development across the RCD community, drawing on lessons learned from early prototyping efforts with ChatRCD. Additionally, the group is also developing cross-disciplinary case studies drawn from authentic AI projects to illustrate how the lifecycle framework is enacted across different project types and RCD roles. To broaden dissemination and adoption, the working group, together with the interest group, plans to collaborate with the HPC-ED project[36] to extend the reach and reuse of these learning resources. Combined, these efforts translate the lifecycle framework into learning materials grounded in RCD practice that support adaptation and reuse of facilitation approaches across diverse AI research contexts.

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